

AN ASSESSMENT OF PARTICIPATORY APPROACH FOR RURAL DEVELOPMENT IN RAEBARELI AND VARANASI DISTRICTS OF UTTAR PRADESH

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Abstract:

Rural development through participatory communication is a social process in which groups with common interests jointly construct a message oriented toward the improvement of their living conditions and the change of unjust social structures. Participatory communication provides all people, including the marginalized, with access to information and communication systems and an equal opportunity to participate in creating new information and challenging existing unjust social practices. Developmental participatory communication posits that communities should be the main protagonists of processes of social change rather than 'passive beneficiaries' of decisions made by foreign experts. In this sense, it questions the view of development as an externally-driven process planned and implemented by Western technical experts. In this article the researcher has investigated the participatory communication approach to acquaint and involve the locals in Raebareli and Varanasi districts of Uttar Pradesh about the rural development programmes in their areas. The researcher has selected two blocks from each districts (Unchhar and Dalmau) from Raebareli and (Chiraigaon and Haruha) from Varanasi. Since each block contains several villages, for the purpose of designed survey, the researcher further selected one village from each block: Kand Rawan from Unchhar block; Aihar from Dalmau block; Bhabhanpura from Chiraigaon block and Lamahi from Haruha block. From this study the researcher tried to investigate the level of awareness among people which directly or indirectly affects their life style and shows their level of participation in the development of their respective areas.

Key Words: Rural Development, Communication Strategies, Participatory Communication & Development Communication

Introduction:

Development is a process of improving the well-being of the people. It is about raising the standard of living of the people, improving their education and health, and also opening out to them new and equal opportunities for a richer and more varied life. "Development is a participatory process of directed social change in a society, intended to bring about social and material advancement (including greater equality, freedom, and other valued qualities) for the majority of people through their gaining greater control over their environment," (Rogers, 1976). The Brandt Commission Report (1979) states, "Development never will be, and never can be, defined to universal satisfaction". With the same notion, "Development is probably one of the most depreciated terms in social science literature, having been used more than it has been understood." (Uphoff and Ilchman, 1972). As development is a complex phenomenon comprising many dimensions social, cultural, economic, political, administrative and so on, we view for social development, economic development, political development, and administrative development. So, while defining development it is mandatory to go for an integrated approach.

Rural development was commonly understood and expressed by political leaders, academics and a whole lot of UN bodies as an enabling force for improvement of the quality of life of rural people. Development, as a process meant to empower the poor, reduce exploitation, and oppression by those having economic, social, and political power. It also means an equitable sharing of resources, improved health care and education for all. One of the major components and driving force of rural development is communication. Persuasive communication for rural development has been given highest priority for bringing about desirable social and behavioural change among the most vulnerable rural poor.

"*Development*" and "*Communication*" are two terms heavily loaded with different conceptions and a richness of uses and functions shaped by their various theoretical underpinnings. Communication media, in the context of development, are generally used to support development initiatives by the dissemination of messages that encourage the public to support development-oriented projects. Although development strategies in developing countries diverge widely, the usual pattern for broadcasting and the press has been predominantly the same: informing the population about projects, illustrating the advantages of these projects, and recommending that they be supported. A typical example of such a strategy is situated in the area of family planning, where communication means such as posters, pamphlets, radio, and television attempt to persuade the public to accept birth control methods. Similar strategies are used in campaigns regarding health and nutrition, agricultural projects, education, and so on (Kaul, 2011).

Communication for development is based on the premise that successful rural development calls for the conscious and active participation of the intended beneficiaries at every stage of the development process. Rural development cannot take place without changes in attitudes and behavior among the people concerned. Communication for development is defined as the planned and systematic use of communication, through inter-personal channels, ICT, audio-visuals and mass media:

- ✓ To collect and exchange information among all those concerned in planning a development initiative with the aim of reaching a consensus on the development problems being faced and the options for their solution.
- ✓ To mobilize people for development action and to assist in solving problems and misunderstandings that may arise during development plan implementation.
- ✓ To enhance the pedagogical and communication skills of development agents (at all levels) so that they may have a more effective dialogue with their audience.
- ✓ To apply communication technology to training and extension programmes, particularly at the grassroots level, in order to improve their quality and impact.

In the past, development communication was used mainly to disseminate information, to make people aware of development's benefits and to install a willingness to follow leaders. This was based on the assumption that newly created wealth or idea would automatically percolate down and "irrigate" the whole society. The new concept of development communication considers 'participation of people' as an important aspect of development communication, taking rural people at the centre of any given development initiative and views planners, development workers, local authorities, farmers and rural people as "communication equals", equally committed to mutual understanding and concerted action. The participatory process in development communication is defined as a two-way, dynamic interaction between grassroots receiver and the information source in a communication transaction.

In the present article the author has investigated the various means of communication used by the subjects in the selected areas of Raebareli and Varanasi districts of Uttar Pradesh. The aim of this study was to find the means by which people remain informed about the various developmental news/ projects of the Government.

Review of Literature:

Rural development is characterised by a mix of theory and practice: "that is both ideas about how 'development' should or might occur, and real world efforts to put various aspects of development into practice." (Potter, 2002). The vision and priorities for rural development closely reflect changing global development trends and relations of power and influence. 'Rural Development: Putting the last first' by Robert Chambers (1983)⁶ evaluates rural poverty which is often unseen or misperceived by outsiders. Chambers contends that researchers, scientists, administrators and fieldworkers rarely appreciate the richness and validity of rural people's knowledge or the hidden nature of rural poverty. He highlights the six biases for the rural poverty un-observed. These six set of biases: (i) Spatial biases: urban, tarmac and roadside, (ii) Project biases, (iii) Person biases, (iv) Dry season biases, (v) Diplomatic biases-politeness and timidity and (vi) Professional biases, are not confined in pursuit of developing rural tourism but validates its core prospects for the scholars and practitioners in the field of rural development.

Histories of thinking about rural development often attempt to periodise different approaches and key ideas by decades. In part these reflect the preoccupations of the four United Nations (UN) development decades which commenced in the 1960s. Hence it is often said that:

- ✓ 1960s were associated with modernisation approaches emphasising technology transfer.
- ✓ 1970s were associated with large scale state development interventions and integrated rural development programmes.
- ✓ 1980s were associated with market liberalisation and attempts to roll back the state.
- ✓ 1990s were characterised as being strongly process focused with an emphasis on participation and empowerment within a context of diversifying rural livelihood opportunities.
- ✓ By end of 1990s a more balanced approach had started to emerge but there remains no agreement worldwide on how to get the right mix. (Ibid)
- ✓ 2000s have focused on poverty eradication, reinvigoration of small holder agriculture, sustainable farming systems and the location of producers within global value chains.

However, according to Ellis and Biggs (2001), rural policies have not evolved in such a neat, linear and schematic manner and that "there are leads and lags in the transmission of new ideas across space and time".

The current decade has been characterised by flux and fragmentation in development thinking and rural development policy despite the overarching focus of attaining the Millennium Development Goals. This has been accompanied by increasing concern about the depoliticisation of issues inherent in policy development processes. It has been argued that rationalist models tend to depoliticise the issues which are the focus of policy through the use of neutral scientific language. 'This masking of the political under the cloak of neutrality is a key feature of modern power (Sutton, 1999). The start of the decade was marked by the dominance of broader

livelihoods approaches which replaced a more conventional and narrow sectoral foci on small farmers, agriculture and the non farm economy. However people have experienced difficulties in practically applying livelihoods thinking to the design of rural development programmes and currently there appears to be a refocusing on the potential of agriculture and natural resources to make a contribution to economic growth and household livelihood security. This has been accompanied by an increasing emphasis on decentralisation and the principle of subsidiarity which holds that decisions need to be taken as close to the citizenry and the local level as possible. There remains a tension between more transdisciplinary thinking and the reassertion of sector wide development approaches. Issues of good governance and decentralisation remain important, but at the same time there has been critique of what passes for participation and the lack of meaningful downward accountability in the decentralisation process. 'Mass Media and Rural Development' by Joni C. Joseph (1997) presents the characteristic feature of the Third World countries that are predominantly rural in character and having agrarian as well as subsistence-oriented economy. The transformation of these countries by structural changes in the total society has been the major emphasis in all the models of development. The role of the media in carrying the message of modern technology to the doorsteps of the rural folk has been examined:

- ✓ To enquire whether there exists any relationship between exposure to mass media and socio-economic development of the rural population; and, if it exists so, to find out the nature and extent of the relationship between the two.
- ✓ To analyze the difference, if any, in the exposure of the rural population to the press, the radio and cinema on account of the differences in the people's age, religions, caste affiliation, income, educational attainment, socio-economic status and residence in areas with different social overheads.
- ✓ To find out the nature of influence of the mass media in the process of rural development.

Mehra Masani (1975) in the book 'Communication and Rural Progress,' a collection of seminar papers mention various useful studies which need to be replicated all over the country. Research must identify problems and explore solutions. Communicators in India have been deprived of accurate data. Possibility of effective rural communication without the area profile covering the major occupational, socio-economic conditions, the age and sex ratios, the opportunities and possibilities of development, and so forth is a big question. For the first time such profiles of villages was prepared for the Satellite Instructional Television Experiment. This was the beginning of systematic studies of the kind all over the country.

The process of communication can have two basic roles to play (a) creation of awareness, through general information and (b) adoption of an innovation through a conscious and planned use of communication tools. Both roles are important and complementary as adoption results out of awareness, if the process is one continuous chain of messages. Techniques and tools of dissemination will, however, differ from area to area depending upon the receptivity of the audience, and their level in the stage of development. By and large, communication tools in developing countries have been designed with a universal approach; to some extent this broad based approach might serve for programs which have a generalized base, for example, education, family planning and others. Agricultural communication, however, becomes more complex when receptivity to innovation is dependent upon a host of variables, which have a direct bearing on how a farm is structured and the stage of transition which it has reached. Before a scientific policy for communication can be developed it becomes necessary for policy makers to have a thorough understanding of the farming systems of their audience. Ranjit Singh (1993) in his book 'Communication Technology for Rural Development' discusses about the various media that can be employed in rural development and blends theory with practical guidelines. The potential contribution of communication media, both modern and traditional, for rural development has been strongly supported by research. The author has highlighted the role of technology in rural development, as stated "Communication technology can play a significant role in developing rural resources and motivating the masses for adoption of new technology. It has the potential to widen horizons, to focus attention, to raise aspirations and to create a climate for development. In addition to transferring technology, communication channels have the potential to confer status, to enforce social norms, to help form tastes and could also affect lightly held attitudes. The challenge is to put the resources and the power of communication skillfully and fully behind economic and social development". Juan D. Bordenave (1977), in his book 'Communication and Rural Development' examines the hypothesis that much recent and present-day use of communication media for rural development does not take adequate account of the theoretical work done so far on the function of communication media in reaching rural adult populations and on the nature of the diffusion process. In other words, to ask: Is there a gap between theory and practice in rural development efforts involving communication media? If such a gap does exist, it indicates how those designing and execution of rural development projects could make better use of theory. The way theoreticians and practitioners could work more closely in the future in solving their communication problems must be given due emphasis.

Misra et al., (2010) in the book, 'Development Concerns in the 21st century' has explored sustainable rural development in India towards the Gandhian framework. Mahatma Gandhi, perhaps the most important thinker and social activist of the century showed India not only the way to win freedom from the British but also to get rid of the tyranny of modern civilization. Gandhi was highly critical of modern civilization, he called it

satanic and said "this civilization is such that one has only to be patient and it will be self-destroyed" (M.K.Gandhi in *Hind Swaraj* p.34). A development model which is unable to remove mass poverty, which fails to bridge the gap between rural and urban areas and between haves and have-nots, and which cannot guaranty even the basic needs (food, clothing, shelter, health, education, security and self-esteem) of the people, can be pursued only to invite chaos- social, economic and moral. Misra has minutely observed the poor standard of rural population living in a vicious circle of poverty and under development. He discussed about the migration issue, where a few migrate to over crowded cities but the cities offer nothing better. Only those who are educated and skilled make migration a success story. The rest are condemned to live in slums and *jhuggi-jhopadis* and to eke out a living from what is known as the informal sector of urban economy. He further examined, no less than 50 per cent of the rural population of India live below the poverty line though the official estimates bring it down to 30 per cent or less. But even 30 per cent means 325 million people. It is more than the total population of all other countries of the world except China.

'Indian Development: Selected Regional Perspectives' by Jean Dreze and Amartya Sen (1997) explores India as a nation of great diversity. The commonly used indicators of 'quality of life' (such as life expectancy, infant mortality, and literacy) vary tremendously between the different states, rivalling international contrasts between very low performing countries and very high achieving ones. This volume of essays reflects an attempt to draw lessons from the disparate experiences within India, rather than from contrasts with the experiences of other countries. It supplements Dreze and Sen's *India: Economic Development and Social Opportunity*, which studies what we can learn from international comparisons of policies, actions, and achievements. The essays challenge exclusively economic judgments of the development process. The first task is to identify the ends of economic and social development in order to have a basis in which to found the means and strategies. The second task is to understand a wider range of means than those related simply to the use or non-use of markets. The first two overview essays study the issues at the national level, focusing on policy debates and district-by-district demographic indicators, respectively. They are followed by detailed case studies of three very different states: Uttar Pradesh, Kerala, and West Bengal. The chapter "Uttar Pradesh: The Burden of Inertia", contributed by Jean Drèze and Haris Gazdar, gives an insight to the problems of economic and social backwardness in Uttar Pradesh and its causal antecedents. Among these are the disastrous functioning of public services in rural areas, the persistence of widespread illiteracy, and the suppression of women's agency in society. This chapter also talks about the social and political circumstances underlying these diverse failures. The term 'inertia' has been significantly used with two aspects, (i) apathy of the state and (ii) failure of civil society to challenge oppressive patterns of caste, class and gender relations. Although the authors focus is on Uttar Pradesh, they argue that the 'inertia' explanation also applies to other backward regions of North India.

Methodology:

In this study, the survey method was used with the help of a structured questionnaire for the rural population in the selected areas of Raebareli and Varanasi. A separate questionnaire was also prepared to examine the views of administrative government officials involved in rural development programmes. The researcher has adopted the sampling method for this study. The convenient sampling for selection of two developed blocks from each district was taken on the basis of villages in which the panchayats have worked and has utilized the government rural funds. Further, the method was also applied to access the beneficiaries of the rural development programs and collect useful information relevant for the study.

Area and Tool Selected for the Study:

The areas selected for the study are Unchahar and Dalmau blocks under Raebareli district; Chiraigaon and Haruha blocks under Varanasi District. One village each from the two blocks of the district has been taken into account for the purpose of selecting the respondents. The researcher developed a questionnaire as a tool for data collection from the selected respondents. The study involved the response of 500 respondents (250 from each district) which have been analyzed in terms of percentages.

Questionnaire and Pre-Testing:

The researcher has conducted a pre test among 20 respondents in the sample villages of the universe. After the pre test some the researcher translated the questionnaire into the language used by the local people so that they can understand the questions. The questionnaire was based on the general information, demographic profile, educational and economical status, awareness about the citizen's rights, the communication usage pattern and developmental strategy for communicating rural development programmes. Here the respondents were asked to rate the performance of media on rural issues and give their critical opinion on the media's role.

Sampling Technique:

The researcher has used non-probability sampling, particularly in the form of available samples. An available sample (also known as convenience sample) is a collection of readily accessible subjects for study, such as group of students enrolled in an introductory mass media course or shoppers in a mall.

Statistical Analysis:

The researcher has applied percent analysis method for interpretation of the data collected through survey in this study.

Result & Discussion:

As shown in table 1, the gender ratio of respondents in selected villages was examined. In Kand Rawan village of Unchahar block, 67.2% males constituted the majority while females were 32.8% out of 125 respondents. In Aihar village of Dalamau block and Lamahi village of Haruha block the male and female percentage was almost equal with 57.6% and 42.4%; 58.4% and 41.6% respectively, out of 125 respondents in each village. The variation in this ratio exceeded in Bhabhanpura village of Chiraigaon with 80.8% males and 19.2% females out of 125 respondents. In the final analysis, the male respondents in all the four villages constituted the majority with 66% as compared to females which was only 34% out of total 500 respondents. This shows that over 69% in Varanasi and over 62% in Raebareli district were male, whereas the female respondents in Raebareli were more with 37.6% in comparison to Varanasi with 30.4%. (Table 1). The age composition as shown in table 1. indicates that out of total 500 respondents, examined in all the four villages of the four blocks, the maximum of 30.6% were in the age group of 35-50yrs, followed by 23.6% of 21-35yrs, 22.4% of 50-60yrs, 15.8% of 60-70yrs group, and only 7.8% of above 70yrs. In aggregate, out of total 500 respondents examined, both Raebareli and Varanasi have the majority of respondents in the age group of 35-50 years and the lowest number of respondents in the above 70 age group with 9.2% and 6.4% respectively. When examined for educational qualification, (Table 1.) it was observed that in aggregate considering all the four villages in their respective blocks, out of the total 500 respondents examined, 43% were of below matriculation, 27% matriculates followed by 20% intermediates, 8.4% graduates and only 1.6% post graduates. Thus, both Raebareli and Varanasi have majority of respondents with below matriculation, matriculation and intermediate qualification.

As shown in table 1. When examined for occupation, it was found that the highest percentage of respondents are farmers (51.6%), followed by laborers (28.2%), private job workers (9.4%), government service holders (8%) and unemployed (2.8%). In aggregate, both the districts have majority of farmer and laborer respondents. In the final analysis, for Below Poverty line card holders, Raebareli has more respondents (71.2%) with BPL cards than non-holders with 28.8%, while in Varanasi above 49% respondents are BPL card holders and above 50% are non-holders. (Table 1) For annual income range analysis, we observed that Raebareli has more respondents in the Rs. 50,000 –1 lakh annual income range as compared to Varanasi where majority respondents were in the below Rs. 50,000 income category. In Varanasi, more than 14% respondents are in the category with more than Rs. 1.5 lakh income category as compared to Raebareli with only 1.2% respondents in this category. (Table 1) In terms of voter card holders, from table 1, it is clear that the highest percentage was of Voter ID card holders in both Raebareli and Varanasi with an aggregate of 76.6%, followed by non-holders with 23.6%. This is in contrast with PAN card holders where it is found that the highest percentage was of PAN card non-holders with 80.4%, followed by 19.6% of those with PAN card in both Raebareli and Varanasi. Similarly when respondents were asked about bank accounts it was found that the highest percentage (53.6%) was of those with no account, followed by 43.8% with one account and only 2.6% have more than one account. In district wise analysis it was observed that in Raebareli, majority of respondents do not have bank account followed by 34.8% of those with one account and only 0.8% with more than one accounts. In Varanasi, more than 52% respondents have only one account while 42.8% have no account and only 4.4% have more than one account. (Table 1)

Table 1: Demographic profile, educational and economic status of the respondents (total 500) who participated in the survey

Districts	Blocks (Village)	Parameters								
		Respondents Gender % (No.)	Age % (No.)	Educational Qualification % (No.)	Occupation % (No.)	BPL Card holder % (No.)	Annual income % (No.)	Voter card holder % (No.)	PAN Card holder % (No.)	Bank accounts % (No.)
Raebareli	Unchahar (Kand Rawan)	Male 67.2 % (84) Female 32.8 % (41)	21-35 18.4 % (23) 35-50 28.8% (36) 50-60 25.6 % (32) 60-70 20 % (25) >70 7.2 % (9)	<HS 52% (65) HS 24% (30) Inter 20.8% (26) UG 2.4% (3) PG 0.8% (1)	Farmer 56% (70) Labourer 24.8% (31) Private job 12.8% (16) Govt. Job 2.4% (3) Unemployed 4% (5)	Yes 69.6% (87) No 30.4% (38)	<50000 28.8% (36) 50000-1 lakh 56% (70) 1-1.5 lakh 12.8% (16) >1.5 lakh 2.4% (3)	Yes 72.8% (91) No 27.2% (34)	Yes 7.2% (9) No 92.8% (116)	1 account 39.2% (49) >1 account 0% (0) No account 60.8% (76)
	Dalamau (Aihar)	Male 57.6 % (72) Female 42.4 % (53)	21-35 29.6 % (37) 35-50 23.21 % (29) 50-60 20 % (25) 60-70 16 % (20) >70 11.2 % (14)	<HS 45.6% (57) HS 32% (40) Inter 21.6% (27) UG 0.8% (1) PG 0% (0)	Farmer 55.2% (69) Labourer 34.4% (43) Private job 8.8% (11) Govt. Job 0% (0) Unemployed 1.6% (2)	Yes 72.8% (91) No 27.2% (34)	<50000 56.8% (71) 50000-1 lakh 34.4% (43) 1-1.5 lakh 8.8% (11) >1.5 lakh 0% (0)	Yes 66.4% (83) No 33.6% (42)	Yes 2.4% (3) No 97.6% (122)	1 account 30.4% (38) >1 account 1.6% (2) No account 68% (85)
Varanasi	Chiraigaon (Bhabhanpura)	Male 80.8 % (101) Female 19.2 % (24)	21-35 20 % (25) 35-50 39.2 % (49) 50-60 20.8% (26) 60-70 11.2 % (14)	<HS 19.2% (24) HS 32.8% (41) Inter 24% (30) UG 0% (0)	Farmer 41.6% (52) Labourer 21.6% (27) Private job 5.6% (7) Govt. Job 0% (0)	Yes 39.2% (49) No 60.8% (76)	<50000 43.2% (54) 50000-1 lakh 21.6% (27) 1-1.5 lakh 5.6% (7)	Yes 88% (110) No 12% (15)	Yes 45.6% (57) No 54.4% (68)	1 account 60.8% (76) >1 account 6.4% (8) No account 32.8% (41)

			% (14) >70 8.8% (11)	18.4% (23) PG 5.6% (7)	29.6% (37) Unemploye d 1.6% (2)		>1.5 lakh 29.6% (37)			
	Haruha (Lamahi)	Male 58.4% (73) Female 41.6% (52)	21-35 25.6% (32) 35-50 31.2% (39) 50-60 23.2% (29) 60-70 16% (20) >70 4% (5)	<HS 55.2% (69) HS 19.2% (24) Inter 13.6% (17) UG 12% (15) PG 0% (0)	Farmer 53.6% (67) Labourer 32% (40) Private job 10.4% (13) Govt. Job 0% (0) Unemploye d 4% (5)	Yes 60% (75) No 40% (50)	<50000 57.6% (72) 50000-1 lakh 32% (40) 1-1.5 lakh 10.4% (13) >1.5 lakh 0% (0)	Yes 79.2% (99) No 20.8% (26)	Yes 23.2% (29) No 76.8% (96)	1 account 44.8% (56) >1 account 2.4% (3) No account 52.8% (66)

As shown in table 2 (village wise), in Kand Rawan village of Unchhar block of Raebareli, majority 65.6% owned mobile sets followed by 34.4% without mobile sets. In Aihar village of Dalmau block of Raebareli, more than 52% were without mobile sets followed by 47.2% with mobile sets. In Bhabhanpura village of Chiraigaon block, Varanasi, the maximum 70.4% owned mobile set while the remaining 29.6% did not. In Lamahi village of Haruha block, Varanasi, 55.2% had mobile set, followed by 44.8% without it. The study shows that in Raebareli 43.6% do not have any mobile set as compared to Varanasi with 37.2%, whereas in Varanasi 62.8% respondents had mobile set, in Raebareli 56.4% respondents were in this category. (Table 2) As analysed for using newspaper as means of awareness and communication, it was observed that in Raebareli including both Unchhar and Dalmau, more respondents (61.6%) were non readers of newspapers whereas in Varanasi including both Chiraigaon and Haruha, more respondents (68%) were newspaper readers. (Table 2) When examined for using radio as means of communication tool, it was found that the highest percentage 74.2% of radio listeners, followed by 25.8% who were non listeners. In the final analysis, both in Raebareli (66%) and Varanasi (82.4%) more respondents were radio listeners. (Table 2) In the final analysis, of respondents using television as media of communication and awareness, the highest percentages (50.6%) of respondents were television viewers, followed by 49.4% non viewers. In Raebareli television non-viewers (69.2%) were more in number when compared to Varanasi where majority respondents (68%) were television viewers. (Table 2)

When analyzed for the operational knowledge of computer it was found that, the highest percentage (84.2%) was of respondents with no operational knowledge, followed by 15.8% with operational knowledge of computer in the selected districts. In village wise analysis, Kand Rawan have majority of respondents, 95.2% do not have any operational knowledge of computer followed by 4.8% with operational knowledge of computer. In Aihar, majority 97.6% do not have any operational knowledge of computer followed by 2.4% with operational knowledge. In Bhabhanpura, the maximum 65.6% were with no operational knowledge while the remaining 34.4% had the operational knowledge. In Lamahi, 98% were with no operational knowledge, followed by 2.4% with operational knowledge of computer. In aggregate, in Raebareli 96.4% does not have any operational knowledge of computer when compared to Varanasi with 72%. While in Varanasi 28% respondents have the operational knowledge of computer, in Raebareli only 3.6% respondents have. As observed out of these respondents, in Raebareli the majority of respondents have no access to internet with 96% as compared to Varanasi with 82.4%. (Table 2).

Table 2: Communication tools used by respondents

Districts	Blocks (Village)	Parameters					
		Mobile users % (No.)	Newspaper readers % (No.)	Radio listeners % (No.)	Television viewers % (No.)	Computer users % (No.)	Subjects with internet access % (No.)
Raebareli	Unchahar (Kand Rawan)	Yes 65.6% (82) No 34.4% (43)	Yes 45.6% (57) No 54.4% (68)	Yes 68.8% (86) No 31.2% (39)	Yes 32.8% (41) No 67.2% (84)	Yes 4.8% (6) No 95.2% (119)	Yes 5.6% (7) No 94.9% (118)
	Dalmau (Aihar)	Yes 47.2% (59) No 52.8% (66)	Yes 31.2% (39) No 68.8% (86)	Yes 63.2% (79) No 36.8% (46)	Yes 28.8% (36) No 71.2% (89)	Yes 2.4% (3) No 97.6% (122)	Yes 2.4% (3) No 97.6% (122)
Varanasi	Chiraigaon (Bhabhanpura)	Yes 70.4% (88) No 29.6% (37)	Yes 78.4% (98) No 21.6% (27)	Yes 90.4% (113) No 9.6% (12)	Yes 82.4% (103) No 17.6% (22)	Yes 34.4% (43) No 65.6% (82)	Yes 26.4% (33) No 73.6% (92)
	Haruha (Lamahi)	Yes 55.2% (69) No 44.8% (56)	Yes 57.6% (72) No 42.4% (53)	Yes 74.4% (93) No 25.6% (32)	Yes 53.6% (67) No 46.4% (58)	Yes 21.6% (27) No 78.4% (98)	Yes 8.8% (11) No 91.2% (114)

Table 3: Variety of information which respondents gather from different media

Districts	Blocks (Village)	Parameters			
		Developmental News %	General News %	Entertainment %	Political %

		% (No.)	(No.)	(No.)	(No.)
Raebareli	Unchahar (Kand Rawan)	16% (20)	44.8% (56)	12% (15)	27.2% (34)
	Dalmau (Aihar)	12% (15)	44% (55)	8.8% (11)	35.2% (44)
Varanasi	Chiraigaon (Bhabhanpura)	24% (30)	24.8% (31)	8% (10)	43.2% (54)
	Haruha (Lamahi)	20% (25)	29.6% (37)	9.6% (12)	40.8% (51)

As shown in Table 3, when analysed for the variety of news that the respondents gather from the different media they use for communication and awareness, it was found that, including all the four villages of the chosen blocks in Raebareli and Varanasi districts of Uttar Pradesh, the highest percentage (more than 36%) was of respondents getting political information from different media, followed by 35.8% getting news, 18% getting developmental information and only 9.6% getting entertainment. It was found that, in Varanasi, the majority of respondents, 42% were getting political information from different media as compared to Raebareli with little above 31%. In comparison to Varanasi with more than 27% respondents getting news information, Raebareli has little more than 44% respondents in this category. In the developmental news category, Varanasi has 22% respondents while Raebareli has 14%. 8.8% of respondents in Varanasi were getting entertainment related information from different media as compared to only 10.4% in Raebareli. (Table 3). As shown in table 4, (village wise), in Kand Rawan, 14.4% were getting information on government welfare schemes through government officials, 11.2% through non-government organizations, 17.6% from both. Those getting information on government welfare schemes by different media sources are 28% from newspaper followed by 18.62% from radio, 10.4% from television and none from internet. In Aihar, 12.8% respondents were getting information on government welfare schemes through government officials, 12% through non-government organizations, 21.6% from both. Those getting information on government welfare schemes by different media sources are 19.2% from newspaper followed by 26.55% from radio, 8% from television and none from internet. In Bhabhanpura, 21.6% were getting information on government welfare schemes through government officials, 11.2% through non-government organizations, 13.6% from both. Those getting information on government welfare schemes by different media sources are 26.4%, from newspaper followed by 8.8% from radio, 16.8% from television and 1.6% from internet. In Lamahi, 15.2% respondents were getting information on government welfare schemes through government officials, 10.4% through non-government organizations, and 14.4% from both. Those getting information on government welfare schemes by different media sources are 30.4% from newspaper followed by 11.2% from radio, 16.8% from television and none from internet. In the final analysis, both Raebareli (23.6%) and Varanasi (28.4%) have more respondents getting information about government development schemes from newspaper and the lowest number are getting information from internet. (Table 4).

Table 4: Various sources of information on government welfare schemes

Districts	Blocks (Village)	Awareness % (No.)	
Raebareli	Unchahar (Kand Rawan)	Yes	35.2% (44)
		No	45.6% (57)
		Average	7.2% (9)
		Very less	12% (15)
Raebareli	Dalmau (Aihar)	Yes	39.2% (49)
		No	42.4% (53)
		Average	10.74% (13)
		Very less	8% (10)
Varanasi	Chiraigaon (Bhabhanpura)	Yes	49.6% (62)
		No	29.6% (37)
		Average	13.6% (17)
		Very less	7.2% (9)
Varanasi	Haruha (Lamahi)	Yes	47.2% (59)
		No	25.98% (32)
		Average	16.8% (21)
		Very less	10.4% (13)

Table 5: Awareness of major government development programs such as MNERGA /NRHM /PMGS /NBS /NSAP 788 011

Districts	Blocks (Village)	Parameters					
		Government officials % (No.)	NGO % (No.)	Media			
				News Paper % (No.)	Radio % (No.)	TV % (No.)	Internet % (No.)
Raebareli	Unchahar (Kand Rawan)	14.4% (18)	11.2% (14)	28% (35)	18.62% (23)	10.4% (13)	0% (0)
	Dalmau (Aihar)	12.8% (16)	12% (15)	19.2% (24)	26.55% (33)	8% (10)	0% (0)
Varanasi	Chiraigaon (Bhabhanpura)	21.6% (27)	11.2% (14)	26.4% (33)	8.8% (11)	16.8% (21)	1.6% (2)
	Haruha (Lamahi)	15.2% (19)	10.4% (13)	30.4% (38)	11.2% (14)	18.4% (23)	0% (0)

The researcher analysed the respondents for Awareness of major government development programs such as MNERGA/NRHM/PMGS/NBS/NSAP (Table 5), and the observation was that in village wise analysis, Kand Rawan has majority of respondents (above 45%) who were not aware of the different rural development schemes followed by those who were aware with 35.2%, very less aware with 12% and average awareness with 7.2%. In Aihar, majority 42.4% respondents were not aware of the different rural development schemes followed by those who were aware with 39.2%, with average awareness 10.74% and very less aware with 8%. In Bhabhanpura, the maximum 49.6% respondents were aware of the different rural development schemes while the remaining 29.6% were not aware of these schemes followed by 13.6% with average awareness and 7.2% with very less awareness. In Lamahi, the majority of 47.2% respondents were aware of the different developmental schemes while the remaining 25.98% were not aware, followed by 16.8% with average awareness and 10.4% were very less aware of the developmental schemes. Overall, the study shows that in Varanasi, the majority of respondents (48.4%) were aware of the rural developmental schemes as compared to Raebareli with 37.2%. In comparison to Raebareli with 44% respondents with no awareness about government developmental schemes, Varanasi has above 27% respondents in this category. In the average awareness category, Varanasi has 15.2% respondents while Raebareli has 8.8%. 10% of respondents in Raebareli had very less awareness about developmental schemes as compared to 8.8% in Varanasi. (Table 5).

Conclusion:

For the required and cutting-edge development of rural India, the coalition between the government and the media is a prime concern as both must blend development with enriched communication to attain successful programming at the grass roots level. Communities, rather than experts or other external agents, should determine challenges and decide appropriate courses of action to tackle problems through dialogue and critical thinking. Locals of any area have a protagonist role in making decisions about the goals and the direction of programs and actions. If decisions are left to agencies and their cadres of professionals, programs and actions are disconnected from the actual motivations and expectations of communities. Local people need to be involved in the implementation of activities. Furthermore, the skills, capabilities, knowledge and support-base of individuals become integral to their capacity to participate in processes that enable them to influence others. The two-way dynamic interaction between grass root receivers and the information source mediated by development communicators must facilitate participation of the target groups in the process of development. A comprehensive review of the communication media for rural development is pertinent to the process of their adoption as an innovation bearing variables of science and technology but in an understanding manner and convenient to the rural masses. Further, the communication strategies must be integrated to generate awareness among the rural masses to persuade them for adopting new set of practices in order to enhance their standard of living.

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